

CHALLENGES ENCOUNTERED BY MATHEMATICS TEACHERS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF CRITICAL THINKING SKILLS AMONG HIGH SCHOOL LEARNERS

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the challenges faced by mathematics teachers in fostering critical thinking skills among high school learners. Utilizing qualitative research methods, including in-depth interviews with ten mathematics teachers, the study identifies several obstacles hindering critical thinking development: learners' lack of prior knowledge, poor reading and comprehension skills, indifference towards math, technology dependency, and passivity. To address these challenges, teachers employ various strategies such as building confidence, encouraging reading, simplifying lessons, leveraging technology, and involving other individuals like parents and peers. Insights from the study highlight the transformative potential of critical thinking, emphasizing its role in problem-solving, decision-making, and independent learning. Recommendations include integrating critical thinking into teacher training, promoting active learning, and providing ongoing support for teachers. Overall, this study underscores the importance of nurturing critical thinking skills to empower learners for success in today's complex world.

Keywords: *Critical Thinking, Mathematics Education, Teaching Strategies*

INTRODUCTION

With the implementation of the K-12 Program in the basic educational system of the country, it is critical and there is an urgent need to enhance quality education in the elementary and high school levels. Teaching learners to become critical thinkers is a common role of education today. Learners can learn to think well if the school's focus is on teaching them how to do so. This is one among its immediate goals.

Critical thinking is one of the two main objectives in mathematics that forms the basis of mathematical learning. Learners typically engage in critical thinking when they question rather than accepting information at face value. The use of critical thinking results in learnable, mastered abilities. It is the logical analysis of concepts, hypotheses, principles, arguments, conclusions, problems, assertions, convictions, and behaviors. This objective will be met via a well-structured and demanding curriculum, a clearly defined set of advanced abilities and procedures, acceptable attitudes and values, and the right resources, considering the various learning environments of Filipino learners (K-12 Curriculum Guide MATHEMATICS).

The development of critical thinking skills among high school learners in mathematics education is influenced by several key factors. Notably, scholars such as Lipman (2003), Awasthi (2016), and Marzano (2007) emphasize the challenges faced by mathematics teachers, including learners' lack of prior knowledge, poor reading comprehension skills, and indifference towards mathematics, technological dependence, and passivity. These challenges are compounded by learners' difficulty in comprehending mathematical concepts within texts, as articulated by the participants. Learners need to know how to think instead of what to think. This is initiated through various teaching strategies; providing skills like critical thinking; assessment methods; and adopting new ways of teacher's preparation (Lagamon, 2014). To improve learners' critical thinking, knowledge, skills, and dispositions, educators can develop instructional pedagogy with purposeful learning activities that encourage critical thinking abilities (Ikala, 2012).

Moreover, the review underscores the pivotal role of educators in addressing these challenges through various strategies, including building learners' confidence, simplifying lessons, utilizing technology, and involving other stakeholders such as parents and peers. This comprehensive literature review provides a nuanced understanding of the multifaceted nature of the obstacles faced by mathematics teachers in fostering critical thinking skills among high school learners and offers valuable insights into effective pedagogical approaches to mitigate these challenges.

In the classroom scenario, the researcher as a secondary mathematics teacher at Jalandoni Memorial National High School for five years now has identified concerns encountered in the context of teaching and learning process which present critical thinking as a determining factor. The term "critical thinking" can cause different contexts. In literature and other resources, various definitions are available, which seek to illuminate the meaning of the term. The researcher is still uncertain of how to define and view critical

thinking skills since it can present us with a variety of ideas and opinions among people. In connection with these, the main concern of the presented research is to determine whether mathematics teachers' ideas regarding the content of the concept of critical thinking are consistent.

The researcher has also noted that learners have unfavorable reaction towards mathematics as a subject. Many learners find mathematics subject difficult, meaningless, and unappealing, which lead them to underdevelop their critical thinking skills, develop unfavorable attitudes toward the subject and eventually make the teachers deal with various challenges that needed to be handled well in class. However, these are only mere observations and are not supported by scientific data. Thus, the researcher is prompted to conduct this study to determine how teachers view critical thinking skills; the challenges that they encountered; and how these challenges being handled by them at Jalandoni Memorial National High School for school year 2020–2021.

Research Questions

This study was conducted to determine the challenges encountered by mathematics teachers in the development of critical thinking skills among high school learners of Jalandoni Memorial National High School for school year 2020–2021.

Specifically, this study sought answers to the following research questions:

1. How do teachers view critical thinking skills?
2. What are the challenges encountered by mathematics teachers in the development of critical thinking skills among high school learners?
3. How do these challenges being handled by mathematics teachers in the development of critical thinking skills among high school learners?

METHODOLOGY

The research methodology employed in this comprehensive study on the challenges faced by mathematics teachers in fostering critical thinking skills among high school learners utilized a qualitative phenomenological approach, integrating in-depth interviews with purposively selected teachers from Jalandoni Memorial National High School for School Year 2020–2021, complemented by thematic analysis to discern recurring themes, aligning with Creswell's emphasis on phenomenology as a qualitative research approach (Creswell, 2013).

Participants

The participants of the study were the ten (10) purposively selected mathematics teachers teaching Mathematics subject at Jalandoni Memorial National High School for school year 2020–2021.

Instruments of the Study

The research instrument employed in this study was a researcher-made interview schedule, comprising three questions aligned with the study's objectives. Data gathering and documentation were facilitated using voice and video recorders, contingent upon participants' consent.

Procedure

The data gathering procedures for the study involved obtaining consent from the University of Iloilo PHIMNA Education Network Graduate School and the Principal of Jalandoni Memorial National High School, as well as individual participants. The researcher conducted interviews in compliance with minimum health protocols mandated by various authorities amidst the pandemic. In-depth interviews were conducted using voice and video recorders, with participants seated together with the researcher to capture their responses. All collected data were consolidated after the series of interviews.

RESULTS

This section presents the descriptive-qualitative analyses of the data gathered to determine the challenges encountered by mathematics teachers in the development of critical thinking skills among high school learners of Jalandoni Memorial National High School for school year 2020–2021.

Teachers' View of Critical Thinking Skills

Mathematics teachers at Jalandoni Memorial National High School perceive critical thinking skills as encompassing logical reasoning and decision making, processing, and sharing of ideas, reflective and independent thinking, deep understanding, and thinking outside the box. They believe critical thinking involves understanding logical connections between ideas, problem solving, self-reflection, and creative thinking. These skills are seen as crucial for making informed decisions, solving problems systematically, and fostering deeper understanding in mathematics education.

Challenges Encountered by Mathematics Teachers in the Development of Critical Thinking Skills among High School Learners

Mathematics teachers encounter several challenges in developing critical thinking skills among high school learners, including learners' lack of prior knowledge, poor reading and comprehension skills, indifference toward the math subject, dependence on technology leading to digital distractions, and passive learning attitudes. These challenges impede the awakening of critical thinking skills essential for effective learning and problem-solving.

How Mathematics Teachers Handle Challenges in the Development of Learners' Critical Thinking Skills

Mathematics teachers address challenges in developing learners' critical thinking skills by encouraging confidence, emphasizing reading comprehension, simplifying lessons, leveraging technology, and fostering interactions with peers, family, and tutors. These approaches aim to empower students and facilitate deeper understanding and application of critical thinking skills.

DISCUSSION

The comprehensive analysis of the challenges encountered by mathematics teachers in developing critical thinking skills among high school learners reveals a multifaceted landscape. Learners' struggle with a range of issues, including poor prior knowledge, reading comprehension deficits, disinterest in mathematics, technological dependence, and passive learning tendencies. To tackle these hurdles, teachers employ diverse strategies. They focus on instilling confidence in learners, encouraging extensive reading, simplifying lessons to enhance relatability, leveraging technology as a teaching aid, and involving various stakeholders such as family members, peers, and tutors. With these diverse teaching strategies, mathematics teachers aim to create conducive learning environment in which critical thinking abilities may develop, ultimately equipping learners with the ability to solve challenging problems and think analytically both within and outside of the classroom.

Conclusions

In conclusion, this study sheds light on the challenges faced by mathematics teachers in nurturing critical thinking skills among high school learners, emphasizing the significance of this endeavor for both teachers and learners. Through in-depth interviews and thematic analysis, it became evident that learners' lack of prior knowledge, poor reading comprehension, indifference toward math, dependence on technology, and passive learning attitudes pose significant hurdles. However, teachers employ various strategies like building confidence, promoting reading, simplifying lessons, integrating technology, and fostering relationships to address these challenges. Insights gleaned underscore the transformative potential of critical thinking, empowering learners to discern, analyze, and solve problems effectively. Recommendations put forth underscore the importance of integrating critical thinking development into teacher training, promoting active learning environments, and providing ongoing support and recognition for teacher. Ultimately, by emphasizing critical thinking, teachers can equip learners with essential life skills to effectively deal the challenges of modern life and contribute meaningfully to society.

Recommendations

In the light of the findings and insights arrived in this study, it is recommended that critical thinking needs to be constantly practiced as through this way, it will train learners how to think, interpret, analyze, and evaluate information that they receive. There is a dire need to promote active learning to produce learners who are independent in their way of thinking and learning. To sustain enthusiasm of the teachers using critical thinking skills, awards and recognition should be institutionalized. Teachers should not only focus on completing the learning competencies as stipulated by the Department of Education but to stress more on enhancing the learners' critical thinking ability in the classroom.

Similar studies related to critical thinking skills are encouraged by including learners, parents, and other subject teachers and to focus on learners' perspective on critical thinking and the ways they would want teachers to assist them in enhancing their critical thinking abilities.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In conducting this study on the challenges encountered by mathematics teachers in the development of critical thinking skills among high school learners, ethical considerations were paramount. The participants' anonymity and confidentiality were strictly maintained throughout the research process, with their informed consent obtained before their involvement. Furthermore, their voluntary participation was emphasized, and they were assured of their right to withdraw from the study at any point without consequence. Additionally, efforts were made to minimize any potential harm or discomfort to the participants, and their responses were treated with respect and sensitivity. Finally, the research adhered to established ethical guidelines and principles, ensuring integrity, transparency, and accountability in all aspects of the study.

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